

THE MEDIATING ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SELF-EFFICACY BETWEEN ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION

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Abstracts

As an important driving force for social and economic development, entrepreneurship has received strong attention from the national government in recent years. There are few relevant studies on the relationship between entrepreneurial intention, especially using entrepreneurial self-efficacy as a mediating variable to explore the leading factors of entrepreneurial intention. This study conducts research on how to improve college students' entrepreneurial intentions, explores the relationship between the entrepreneurial environment and college students' entrepreneurial intentions, and introduces entrepreneurial self-efficacy as an intermediary variable to explore the factors that affect entrepreneurial intentions. This study adopts the questionnaire survey method, selected 260 graduates from Aba Teachers' College as subjects, and uses descriptive statistics, t test, variance analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis, Bootstrap test and other statistical methods to analyze the data. This study builds a relationship model between entrepreneurial environment, entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention based on combing the existing relevant domestic and foreign literature, and puts forward the research hypothesis of this article.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Environment, Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy, Entrepreneurial Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since Premier Li Keqiang put forward "mass entrepreneurship, mass innovation", college students' entrepreneurship has become a hot topic of college students' related research. Encouraging college students to start their own business can not only solve the current employment difficulties faced by college students, but also vigorously promote the sound and rapid development of the national economy.

However, at present, college students' entrepreneurship exists the problems of low entrepreneurial ratio and low entrepreneurial success rate, therefore, how to improve the entrepreneurial behavior of college students, enhance their entrepreneurial willingness, and let more college students participate in entrepreneurial activities has an important significance.

Therefore, this paper provides scientific theoretical basis and effective policy suggestions for the cultivation of entrepreneurial talents from multiple perspectives by studying the influencing factors of college students' entrepreneurial willingness as well as the functioning mechanism.

1.1 Background of the Study

With the transformation process of China's market economy and the increasing pressure of employment in the current society, entrepreneurship has gradually become an alternative choice for people choosing jobs, and entrepreneurial activities are playing an increasingly important role. College students, as a young and special group of people with high knowledge level, have rich knowledge reserves and creativity, as well as the courage to try and explore, which is the main group of people who can drive the entrepreneurial boom and entrepreneurial activities. In recent years, the number of fresh graduates from colleges and universities in China has been increasing, with the number of graduates reaching a new record high of 11.58 million in 2023, and the pressure of employment has been increasing. China's economy is affected by the epidemic and the global economic slowdown, China's general economic development is weak, affecting employment and entrepreneurship. Under the fluctuating market environment, college graduates are more cautious about career planning and tend to choose more stable employment.

Therefore, encouraging and guiding college students to start their own business is conducive to solving the problem of employment pressure faced by college students, and at the same time, it can give full play to the creativity of college students, and promote the national economy to develop in a good and fast manner.

In summary, it is of great significance to study the specific influence mechanism of college students' entrepreneurial willingness. Based on this, this paper takes the senior undergraduates of six universities in Sichuan ethnic areas as the research object, and conducts a more systematic and comprehensive research on the various influencing factors and the specific mechanism of college students' entrepreneurial willingness. It aims to assist college students to become better entrepreneurs, to provide guidance for universities to develop entrepreneurial talents, and to provide suggestions for the government and other relevant departments to formulate policies and promote the development of college students' entrepreneurial activities.

1.2 Statement Problem

Since the 21st century, the world's new economic growth is increasingly dependent on information, science and technology, innovation and creativity represented by the knowledge factor, knowledge has become the most dynamic factor of production, the economic growth model more and more emphasis on the traditional factor-driven and input-driven gradual transformation to innovation-driven development. In the face of competition and challenges to accelerate the realization of China's national modernization and national rejuvenation of the historic task, there is an urgent need for a large number of scientists, entrepreneurs and other innovative and entrepreneurial talents. The university students, as the army of social innovation and entrepreneurship, are an important force for the country to realize the goal of innovation-driven development and modernization of the country. Promoting the cultivation of entrepreneurial talents requires attention to the entrepreneurial willingness of college students.

1.3 Research Question

This study addresses the following questions:

- What is the impact of entrepreneurial environment on Entrepreneurial self-efficacy in the university?
- Does entrepreneurial self-efficacy affect the entrepreneurial intention?
- What is the impact of entrepreneurial environment on the entrepreneurial intention?
- Does entrepreneurial self-efficacy mediate the relationship between entrepreneurial environment and the entrepreneurial intention?

1.4 Research Objective

- To examine the impact of Entrepreneurial environment on Entrepreneurial self-efficacy in the university.
- To study the relationship between the Entrepreneurial self-efficacy and the Entrepreneurial intention.
- To measure the impact of Entrepreneurial environment on the Entrepreneurial intention.
- Examine the mediating impact of the Entrepreneurial self-efficacy between Entrepreneurial environment and the Entrepreneurial intention.

1.5 Research Model

Figure 1.1: Research Model

1.6 Hypothesis

- H1:** Entrepreneurial environment has a positive impact on Entrepreneurial self-efficacy
- H2:** Entrepreneurial environment has a positive impact on Entrepreneurial intention
- H3:** Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has a positive impact on Entrepreneurial intention
- H4:** Entrepreneurial self-efficacy mediates the relationship between Entrepreneurial environment and Entrepreneurial intention

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Entrepreneurial Environment

Comprehensive research at home and abroad, the connotation of the entrepreneurial environment can be categorized into three categories:

- 1) **Platform Theory:** The entrepreneurial environment is regarded as the stage for entrepreneurial activities, and the public platform built by the government and society for entrepreneurs to create new enterprises;
- 2) **Factor Theory:** All the comprehensive factors that have an impact on the growth of new enterprises, including economic development, social culture, political policy and other external factors; also includes the support and help provided by the external environment during the growth of the enterprise. Gnyawail & Fogel both define the entrepreneurial environment as all the comprehensive factors that will have an impact on the success or failure of the enterprise during the growth of the new enterprise (Gnyawail & Fogel, 1994);
- 3) **Organic Holism:** Entrepreneurial environment is an organic whole produced by the interaction of various factors that have an impact on the organization or enterprise (Gartner, 1990).

This paper draws on the above research of scholars inside and outside the same, therefore, the entrepreneurial environment of students is defined as the organic whole of various factors that students must face and influence their behavior in the process of implementing entrepreneurial activities. This study divides the entrepreneurial environment of college students into three parts: social environment, school environment, and family environment.

2.2 Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy

The first to introduce Bandura's concept and theory of self-efficacy to the study of entrepreneurship is the scholars Boya & Vozikis, Boyd combined self-efficacy and entrepreneurship field, that individuals have their own judgments and beliefs about being able to successfully play the entrepreneurial role in completing entrepreneurial tasks and the strength of such beliefs is known as entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Boyd, 1994); Scholars Krueger & Brazea argued that individuals are able to convert failure knowledge and perception into their own entrepreneurial experience, and that entrepreneurs characterize their individual entrepreneurial competence and self-control as entrepreneurial self-efficacy. In 1998, Chen pointed out that entrepreneurial self-efficacy is a product of applying self-efficacy theories to the field of entrepreneurship research (Chen, 1998). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy refers to one's own commitment and beliefs about the attainment of the expected outcomes, and higher self-efficacy promotes an individual's ability to learn and risk-taking, thus strengthening entrepreneurial intentions (Tsai, 2016; Schjoedt, 2017).

Domestic scholars have studied entrepreneurial self-efficacy based on the above concepts of foreign scholars, Han (2009) pointed out that entrepreneurial self-efficacy is an individual's perception of his or her ability to accomplish entrepreneurial-related tasks or entrepreneurial behaviors, or it can be described as an individual's confidence and belief in his or her ability to

accomplish entrepreneurial behavioral goals (Han, 2013). Ding Minglei believes that entrepreneurial self-efficacy is an individual entrepreneur's belief that he or she is capable of performing different entrepreneurial roles and believes that he or she is able to accomplish the tasks of entrepreneurial activities (Ding, 2009).

This study defines college students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy as their beliefs and confidence in utilizing their own knowledge and abilities to carry out entrepreneurial activities and successfully create a new business by using the external environment and resources. At present, there is no unified method to measure entrepreneurial self-efficacy in existing literature, specific scales are mostly designed based on research subjects and research scenarios.

2.3 Entrepreneurial Intention

Krueger pointed out that Entrepreneurial Intention is a good predictor of entrepreneurial behavior, and can be used to describe the degree of entrepreneurial traits and subjective attitudes towards the likelihood of a potential entrepreneur choosing to engage in entrepreneurial activities (Krueger, 1993). Phillip used a sample of Singaporean students to study the entrepreneurial intentions of students, he pointed out that entrepreneurial intention refers to the possibility of potential entrepreneurs to choose to start their own business (Philip, 2002). Qian (2007) pointed out that entrepreneurial intention is the potential entrepreneurs in the subjective intention to their own entrepreneurial activities, that is, "to be or not to be", and that entrepreneurship is not an entrepreneurial activity. The question of "to be or not to be".

This paper draws on the definition of entrepreneurial intention by its internal and external scholars to argue that entrepreneurial intention is the subjective attitude of potential entrepreneurs towards whether or not they want to engage in entrepreneurial activities, set up a business, and play the role of an entrepreneur, and it is the question of "to start a business or not to start a business". This study utilizes confirmatory factor analysis, further disentangle these tendencies into two principal aspects: the desirability and feasibility of entrepreneurship.

2.4 Research Gap

First, most of the previous studies on entrepreneurial theories such as entrepreneurial environment and entrepreneurial self-efficacy have been conducted on entrepreneurial groups that have already entered the society, while the present study aims at school college students to study the relationship between entrepreneurial environment, entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention of college students.

Second, Introducing entrepreneurial self-efficacy as a mediating variable. Based on the cognitive theory and the theory of planned behavior, this study conducts research on the relationship between the antecedent variable of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial environment, and the dependent variable, entrepreneurial intention, and explores the mediating effect of entrepreneurial self-efficacy in the relationship between entrepreneurial environment and entrepreneurial intention among college students, which is a new expansion of the research on entrepreneurial self-efficacy and the relationship between entrepreneurial environment and entrepreneurial intention.

3. METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW

This section explains in detail the methodology implemented for this study. A quantitative research strategy was used in this study, where the positivism research approach was used, Quantitative information accumulation strategies are considerably more organized than qualitative information-gathering method (DeFranzo, S. E. 2011). A Non-Probability approach and convenient sampling technique were used in this study.

The population frame of this study was the 2024 graduates of Aba Teachers' College. Entrepreneurial environment was measured with the help of a questionnaire used by Xiao (2021). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy was measured through the questionnaire used by Jill et al., (2005). While Entrepreneurial intention uses the scale developed by Li & Chen (2009).

Ma et al. (2022) made a significant contribution in the area of statistics and research methods. They proposed that the estimated sample size should be 20 times the number of observed variables. In this study, 9 observed variables are proposed and the sample size is estimated to be at least 180.

A structural equation modelling technique was used to test the model. Data were examined with the help of statistical software SMART-PLS Version 4. This software is widely used in the social sciences (DeFranzo SE, 2011; Mansoor A et al., 2020).

The PLS method is a proven method for estimating the path coefficients of structural models. It is increasingly used in social sciences research because of its ability to test the model under non-normality conditions with small to medium samples (Hair JF et al., 2013).

The PLS algorithm defines the significant loadings, weighs and path coefficients, and its bootstrap method determines the significance level of the hypothesis and mediation, therefore a two-stage approach was used in this study, in the first stage the measurement model was assessed and in the second stage, the structural model was assessed.

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1. Reliability and Validity

As described earlier in the methodology section, this study followed the (Hair JF et al., 2013) The model was tested in two stages as suggested by, the first stage assessed the measurement model through the Cronbach's alpha. The Cronbach's alpha values for all variable dimensions range from 0.861 ~ 0.936.

These values show a range of dimensions with significantly high internal consistency, reflecting the reliability and consistency of the items within each scale. The recommended values for Average Variance extraction, Composite Reliability and Factor Loadings should be more than 0.5 and 0.7 respectively (Chin WW.2008).

Table 4.1 shows that the average variance extracted (AVE), composite reliability (CR) and factor loadings for all indicators of the three variables (Entrepreneurial environment, Entrepreneurial self-efficacy and Entrepreneurial intentions) are more than 0.7.

Table 4.1: Validity and Reliability for Constructs

Variables	Dimension	Items	Cronbach's alpha	Loadings	CR	AVE
Entrepreneurial environment (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.933)	School environment	SCE1	0.866	0.854	0.908	0.713
		SCE2		0.831		
		SCE3		0.862		
		SCE4		0.828		
	Social environment	SOE1	0.909	0.82	0.93	0.689
		SOE2		0.85		
		SOE3		0.806		
		SOE4		0.888		
		SOE5		0.827		
		SOE6		0.784		
	Family environment	FE1	0.861	0.899	0.915	0.783
		FE2		0.889		
FE3		0.867				
Entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.965)	Management effectiveness	ME1	0.912	0.803	0.932	0.695
		ME2		0.839		
		ME3		0.887		
		ME4		0.805		
		ME5		0.803		
		ME6		0.861		
	Risk tolerance effectiveness	RTE1	0.843	0.863	0.895	0.68
		RTE2		0.83		
		RTE3		0.777		
		RTE4		0.827		
	Opportunity identification effectiveness	OE1	0.91	0.89	0.937	0.788
		OE2		0.886		
		OE3		0.896		
		OE4		0.88		
	Relationship effectiveness	RE1	0.913	0.908	0.939	0.794
		RE2		0.879		
RE3		0.853				
RE4		0.922				
Entrepreneurial intentions (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.945)	Entrepreneurial desirability	ED1	0.936	0.935	0.959	0.887
		ED2		0.955		
		ED3		0.934		
	Entrepreneurial feasibility	EF1	0.878	0.895	0.925	0.804
		EF2		0.908		
		EF3		0.877		

Discriminant validity indicates the extent to which the measures are not impressions of some other factor, as evidenced by the low relationship between measures of interest and measures of other concepts. As can be seen in Table 4.1, the square root of the AVE (diagonal value) for each variable is greater than the matched correlation measure, indicating a satisfactory direction of discriminant validity (Son TT et al., 2020). Overall, the measurement model has satisfactory convergent and discriminant validity.

Table 4.2: The first structure-Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

	ED	EF	FE	ME	OE	RE	RTE	SCE	SOE
ED	0.942								
EF	0.862	0.897							
FE	0.587	0.54	0.885						
ME	0.493	0.451	0.541	0.834					
OE	0.585	0.576	0.502	0.75	0.888				
RE	0.553	0.537	0.48	0.818	0.834	0.891			
RTE	0.585	0.527	0.506	0.808	0.859	0.798	0.825		
SCE	0.303	0.289	0.517	0.439	0.381	0.416	0.353	0.844	
SOE	0.31	0.321	0.606	0.57	0.472	0.473	0.486	0.75	0.83

Table 4.3: The Second Structure-Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

	Entrepreneurial environment	Entrepreneurial intentions	Entrepreneurial self-efficacy
Entrepreneurial environment	0.745		
Entrepreneurial intentions	0.44	0.887	
Entrepreneurial self-efficacy	0.586	0.599	0.792

4.2 Structural Model

Figure 4.1: Structural Model Results

In the second phase of model testing, the authors tested hypothesized significance levels and mediators using the PLS algorithm and bootstrapping. The bootstrapping was performed for 5000 iterations of the bundling process to check the significance level.

The results of the regression model for entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intentions are shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Regression

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Entrepreneurial self-efficacy	0.344	0.341
Entrepreneurial intentions	0.370	0.366

Chin et al. (2008) classified the dependent variable as "large", "reasonable" and "low", centred on the value of R^2 , the value of R^2 of 0.67 and above indicates a strong effect, the value of R of 0.33 and above indicates a medium effect, and the value of R of 0.19 indicates a weak effect. A value of 0.33 and above indicates a medium effect, and a value of 0.19 for R^2 indicates a weak effect. The value of R^2 for entrepreneurial self-efficacy is 0.344 and the adjusted R^2 is 0.341 and the value of R^2 for entrepreneurial intentions is 0.370 and the adjusted R^2 is 0.366. This shows that entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intentions are moderately affected by Entrepreneurial environment, therefore, the this shows that entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intentions are moderately affected by Entrepreneurial environment, therefore, the significant variance is observed in an endogenous variable.

The results of the structural modelling and hypothesis testing are shown in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Decision
Entrepreneurial environment -> Entrepreneurial intentions	0.44	6.454	0.000	Accepted
Entrepreneurial environment -> Entrepreneurial self-efficacy	0.586	8.015	0.000	Accepted
Entrepreneurial self-efficacy -> Entrepreneurial intentions	0.519	5.6	0.000	Accepted
Entrepreneurial environment -> Entrepreneurial self-efficacy -> Entrepreneurial intentions	0.304	4.256	0.000	Accepted

A total of three hypotheses were tested in this study and all hypotheses were significantly positive. Total 4 hypotheses are being tested in this study, and all hypotheses were found significant and positive. Entrepreneurial environment has a significant and positive effect on Entrepreneurial intentions ($\beta=0.44$, $t=6.454$, $p=0.000$), as well as Entrepreneurial environment has a significant and positive effect on Entrepreneurial self-efficacy ($\beta=0.586$, $t=8.015$, $p=0.000$), and this study also found that Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has a significant and positive effect on Entrepreneurial intentions ($\beta=0.519$, $t=5.6$, $p=0.000$). Finally, this study also concluded that Entrepreneurial self-efficacy also partially mediated the relationship between Entrepreneurial environment and Entrepreneurial intentions ($\beta=0.304$, $t=4.256$, $p=0.000$).

The effect size f^2 describes the influence of exogenous latent construal's on endogenous latent construal's, as mentioned by Hair et al. (2013) (Cohen J, 1988) suggested f^2 sizes of 0.35 (showing large effects), 0.15 (showing medium effects) and 0.02 (showing small effects). f^2 results, as shown in Table 4.5, reveal the range of effect sizes between large and medium effects in this study.

Table 4.6: The Value of f^2

	f-square
Entrepreneurial environment -> Entrepreneurial intentions	0.019
Entrepreneurial environment -> Entrepreneurial self-efficacy	0.524
Entrepreneurial self-efficacy -> Entrepreneurial intentions	0.281

The effect size (f^2) of entrepreneurial environment on entrepreneurial self-efficacy was 0.524 which is considered as a large effect size, The effect size (f^2) of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intentions is 0.281, which is a medium effect size, similarly, the effect size of entrepreneurial environment on entrepreneurial intentions is 0.019, which is a small effect size.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Discussion

This study is based on self-efficacy theory and triadic interaction theory, and conducts a study on the entrepreneurial environment of college students, the relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention, and the mediating role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy in the relationship between entrepreneurial environment and entrepreneurial intention. Analysis and inspection. Empirical analysis results show that entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial environment significantly promote the emergence of individual entrepreneurial intention, and entrepreneurial environment enhances individual entrepreneurial intention through entrepreneurial self-efficacy, that is, entrepreneurial self-efficacy plays a mediating role between the two.

5.2 Research Contribution

This study permits others to understand the impact of Entrepreneurial environment on Entrepreneurial self-efficacy on Entrepreneurial intentions, as well as the mediating role of Entrepreneurial self-efficacy between Entrepreneurial environment and Entrepreneurial intentions. This study contributes to the existing research literature on Entrepreneurial self-efficacy on Entrepreneurial intentions. Previous literature has rarely discussed the impact of Entrepreneurial environment on Entrepreneurial intentions, through their mediating effect on Entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

5.3 Research Implications

Based on domestic and foreign entrepreneurship research, domestic and foreign scholars have done more research on the influencing factors of entrepreneurial intention, but less research on the impact of entrepreneurial environment on entrepreneurial intention. Drawing on relevant research findings, this study developed a research model to test the mediating role of

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy between Entrepreneurial environments on Entrepreneurial intentions. Through the empirical research of this article, we can put forward suggested strategies to improve the entrepreneurial environment of college students and improve their entrepreneurial self-efficacy, thereby enhancing the entrepreneurial behavior of college students and providing more implementation ways to solve the employment problems of college students.

5.4 Theoretical Implications

This article integrates the three variables of college students' entrepreneurial environment, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and entrepreneurial intention into a framework, and combines domestic and foreign research results to construct a scale for college students' entrepreneurial environment and college students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy, which will broaden the scope of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Theory, enrich relevant research on entrepreneurial intention, and enrich the content of college student entrepreneurship research in the context of Chinese culture.

5.5 Practical Implications

From a practical point of view, in China, the highest proportion of entrepreneurs has always been the entrepreneurial group with primary education, while the proportion of college student entrepreneurs is smaller. On the one hand, it is due to the career plans and individual qualities of college students themselves. On the other hand, the entrepreneurial environment will also have an impact on college students' entrepreneurial intentions. With the development of society, mankind has gradually entered the era of knowledge economy, and innovation has become the theme of the era; as our country's economy enters a new normal, breaking through the middle-income trap must rely on innovation to promote it. Under this dual background, it is of great practical significance to study the relationship between entrepreneurial environment, entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention with college students as the main body. Finally, this article also proposes several ways to improve the entrepreneurial environment of college students, improve their entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and enhance their entrepreneurial confidence and belief, thereby contributing to the development of the entrepreneurial economy.

5.6 Limitations

This study mainly has the following shortcomings: First, This study only focused on Aha Teachers' College and obtained 260 valid questionnaires. Therefore, the selection of sample colleges may have certain limitations. Second, through the descriptive statistics of the sample, we found that only 5.76% of the students had actual entrepreneurial experience, while 94.24% of the students had never been engaged in entrepreneurship. Therefore, this study may cause this study to be inaccurate in judging the attitude of college students towards entrepreneurship. Perceptions of the environment and entrepreneurial self-efficacy of college students are sometimes biased. However, during the later data processing and statistical analysis, we found that the sample data still had good reliability and validity, which also proved the rationality of the model and measurement scale design of this study. Third, although we used gender, age,

major, education and entrepreneurial experience as control variables when conducting questionnaire surveys and analyses, there are many factors that can actually affect entrepreneurial intention, such as personality traits and endogenous attitudes. And exogenous attitudes, social relationships, etc., as well as some other accidental factors. This study did not take these factors into account.

5.7 Future Studies

In this study, the researcher has focused only on the 2024 graduates of Aha Teachers' College, a more varied number of participants could have been included in future study and there are chances that the outputs might be changed. Meanwhile, entrepreneurial self-efficacy is still a very new concept. In the future, scholars can study the pre-variables that affect entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and conduct a more in-depth study of the relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial pre-variables. The mediating role of the relationship between intention, entrepreneurial performance, entrepreneurial behavior, etc., and exploring the mechanism of entrepreneurial self-efficacy can better exert the application value of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Future research can explore the true impact on college students' entrepreneurial intention. What are the influencing factors, what is the mechanism of action, and how these factors work together to influence entrepreneurial intention.

5.8 Conclusion

After the above investigation and questionnaire analysis, we came to the following conclusions: The entrepreneurial environment has a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial self-efficacy;

The entrepreneurial environment has a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial intention; Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial intention; Entrepreneurial self-efficacy plays a mediating role in the impact of entrepreneurial environment on entrepreneurial intention.

5.9 Recommendations

College student entrepreneurs are the young people with the highest entrepreneurial enthusiasm, passion and innovative ability among the entrepreneurial group. The government, schools, and society should provide a high-quality entrepreneurial environment for college students to start their own businesses, which can improve college students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

In order to improve college students' entrepreneurial self-confidence, government agencies provide better entrepreneurship policies for college students, universities can invite local famous and successful entrepreneurs to share their entrepreneurial stories and hold entrepreneurial sharing sessions. Parents and relatives and friends around them should actively encourage and support college students' entrepreneurial activities.

College students themselves must also establish ideals and lofty goals, improve their knowledge and comprehensive quality, pursue continuous transcendence, continuous progress, and accumulate innovative spirit.

References

- 1) Boyd, N. G., & Vozikis, G. S. (1994). The influence of self-efficacy on the development of entrepreneurial intentions and actions. *Entrepreneurship: Theory & Practice*, 18, 63-77.
- 2) Chen, C. C., Greene, P. G., & Crick, A. (1998). Does entrepreneurial self-efficacy distinguish entrepreneurs from managers? *Journal of Business Venturing*, 13(4), 295-316.
- 3) Chen, H. S., & Lin, C. (2017). The relationship between entrepreneurial learning and entrepreneurial intention: The role of social networks and entrepreneurial self-efficacy. *Economics and Management Review*, 33(05), 28-33.
- 4) Chin WW, Peterson RA, Brown PS. Structural equation modeling in marketing: Some practical reminders. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*. 2008;16(4):287-98.
- 5) Cohen J. *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). New Jersey, USA: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates. 1988.
- 6) De Noble, A. F., Jung, D., & Ehrlich, S. B. (1999). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy: The development of a measure and its relationship to entrepreneurial action. *Frontiers of entrepreneurship research*, 1999(1), 73-87.
- 7) DeFranzo SE. What's the difference between qualitative and quantitative research? (2011, Sep 16). Retrieved from <https://www.snapsurveys.com/blog/qualitative-vs-quantitative-research/>
- 8) Ding, M., Yang, F., & Wang, Y. (2009). An analysis of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and its impact on entrepreneurial intentions. *Foreign Economics & Management*, 5, 1-7.
- 9) Gartner, W. B., & Bird, B. (1990). What are we talking about when we talk about entrepreneurship? *Social Science Electronic Publishing*, 5(1), 15-28.
- 10) Gnyawali, D. R., & Fogel, D. S. (1994). Environments for entrepreneurship development: Key dimensions and research implications. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 18(4), 43-62.
- 11) Hair JF, Hult GTM, Ringle C, Sarstedt M. *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage Publications. 2013.
- 12) Han, L. (2013). *Can I Start a Business? A study on the structure of entrepreneurial self-efficacy among college students*. (Master's thesis). Nanjing: Nanjing University Press. (pp. 23-30).
- 13) Jill, K., & D'Intino, R. S. (2005). Measure for measure: Modeling entrepreneurial self-efficacy onto instrumental tasks within the new venture creation process. *New England Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 8(2), 39-47.
- 14) Krueger Jr, N. F., & Brazeal, D. V. (1994). Entrepreneurial potential and potential entrepreneurs. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 18(3), 91-104.
- 15) Krueger, N. F. (1993). The impact of prior entrepreneurial exposure on perceptions of new venture feasibility and desirability. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 18(5), 5-11.
- 16) Mansoor A, Farrukh M, Wu Y, Abdul Wahab S. Does inclusive leadership incite innovative work behavior? *Human Systems Management*. 2020,1-10.doi:10.3233/hsm-200972.
- 17) Son TT, Phong LB, Loan BTT. Transformational Leadership and Knowledge Sharing: Determinants of Firm's Operational and Financial Performance. *SAGE Open*. 2020;10(2):2158244020927426.
- 18) Tsai, K. H., Chang, H. C., & Peng, C. Y. (2016). Extending the link between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and intention: A moderated mediation model. *International Entrepreneurship & Management Journal*, 12(2), 445-463. Xiao, T. (2021). The impact of entrepreneurial environment on university students' entrepreneurial intentions.